

Self-service Monitoring of HPC and Openstack Jobs for Users

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Abstract—Using correctly the compute capacity of an HPC or Openstack cluster is often a stumbling block for users, especially those from non-traditional domains where a cluster is only a tool and not the subject of their research.

This paper describes a web portal called *TrailblazingTurtle* built for HPC and Openstack Cluster to let users view the resources used and wasted by their jobs, without having to modify their workflow. The metrics are collected from various data sources on the cluster to enable monitoring at the job and VM level and are presented to the users and staff members as a simple web application. This platform makes it easy for newer users to request the correct quantity of computing resources for their work, see their impact on the shared file system, and the evolution of the priority of their group in Slurm. This helped accelerate research by making sure the users are using the parallel capabilities of their applications and also reduce CPU cycles wasted by right-sizing compute jobs.

This tool also presents an estimation of the energy used and CO2 emission based on the power used by the nodes and their GPUs. A cost comparison with the commercial cloud can also be estimated and presented to the users.

Index Terms—Monitoring, Openstack, Slurm, Prometheus, Grafana, Django

I. INTRODUCTION

Getting the best performance and throughput out of an HPC cluster is something every user and hosting site wants, but is difficult to accomplish without the right tools.

Gathering node-level metrics is something that has been done for at least 20 years on most large HPC clusters with dedicated tools like Ganglia that were built to do exactly that kind of cluster monitoring, but node-level monitoring is not enough to understand the performance of a specific job. Tools like Ganglia are also losing precision over time because of the RRD (Round Robin Database) architecture that is used to store the metrics.

Multiple profiling tools have been developed to help developers optimize their code but required users to modify their workflow to use them. This is not always possible for users that are not familiar with the cluster and are not the developers of the application they are running. The information collected by a profiler is also not available to analysts or

system administrators to have a global view of the cluster usage and to help the right users that need it the most.

The monitoring of jobs and VMs is not as mature as node-level monitoring and there is no standard way to do it. An approach was presented in [Chan(2019)], while being integrated with the Slurm scheduler, it does not extract the information when a node is shared or handles GPU devices.

This paper will present multiple exporters that were created or adapted to extract the information needed to monitor jobs and VMs on an HPC cluster and Openstack cluster. Those exporters can be used directly with Prometheus and Grafana by system administrators.

Presenting all of that information to the users is also a challenge. Most of the time, the users are not interested in the details of the cluster and just want to know if their jobs are running and if they are using the resources they requested. Thus a portal called *TrailblazingTurtle* [Guilbault(2022c)] was built to present the information in a simple way to the users. This portal is the subject of the second half of this paper.

The various graphs presented in this paper are from the Narval cluster operated by Calcul Québec, they represent real users and jobs. Actual names are redacted.

Figure 1 shows an overview of the information flow between the different components.

II. SLURM'S TOOLS

The Slurm HPC scheduler contains a few tools like `seff` that enable basic job monitoring, but it only returns a single number for memory and CPU efficiency. An example of the returned data is in figure 2. Having a single number makes it difficult to see if some section of the applications is not running in parallel and makes it harder to determine how the memory is used over time to see if the Out of Memory error was caused suddenly, or if it looks like a gradual memory leak.

Slurm also has a plugin called `acct_gather_profile/hdf5` [SchedMD(2022)] to gather node statistics and store it in an HDF5 file on the shared file system.

The HDF5 plugin was not retained as a solution for us because it required the compute nodes to have full write access to the file system with the root user (not root-squashed). The plugins also currently lack statistics about accelerators like NVIDIA GPUs. Handling files on a shared file system is also

Fig. 1. The flow of information between the different components

Fig. 2. An example of the information returned by `seff`

```

$ seff 12345678
Job ID: 12345678
Cluster: narval
User/Group: jsmith/jsmith
State: COMPLETED (exit code 0)
Cores: 1
CPU Utilized: 02:48:58
CPU Efficiency: 99.72% of 02:49:26 core-walltime
Job Wall-clock time: 02:49:26
Memory Utilized: 213.85 MB
Memory Efficiency: 0.17% of 125.00 GB

```

more complicated to make them available via a web portal. Having the data in an external time series database also enables us to have a live view of the running jobs without waiting for a file to be updated.

III. COLLECTING METRICS

A. Prometheus and Thanos

We have selected Prometheus [Rabenstein and Volz(2015)] due to multiple factors, such as its easy installation, management, and performance. The initial setup of Prometheus only took us a day, the advantages of the single Go binary made it straightforward to deploy in a test VM. Likewise, the recommended `node_exporter` was also easy to deploy on the stateless compute nodes, the binary only had to be copied inside the image and started.

The other advantage of using a time-series database instead of RDD graphs is that we do not lose any precision as the data is getting older, and we can also do mathematical operations weeks after the data was acquired. Prometheus is normally used with a small amount of local storage, and a data expiration schedule of a few weeks. Since we want to keep

the statistics for a few months about our system and users, we added Thanos, a plugin to enable efficient long-term storage on object storage.

Using Thanos also made queries over multiple clusters possible without having to handle them in the client application by doing multiple connections and having to merge the results. Using a single API call, we can do a query to sum up the use of a single user over all our configured clusters and have the response in a few seconds. This feature can also be used to spread Prometheus on multiple servers for larger HPC systems or HA purposes by having a pair of Prometheus servers gather the same metrics.

The Prometheus VM is using on average 5 cores, 50 GB of memory, 10 IOPS, and 300 GB of local SSD for a week of local retention. This VM is collecting 170k metrics per minute for our 80k cores HPC cluster.

We currently keep all metrics for 9 months for multiple clusters, using 27 TB of object storage for more than 100k monitored cores. The clusters are recording about 370k metrics per minute. After 9 months, we use the Thanos rewrite features to remove job statistics to reduce the storage requirement by 90%.

B. Data collection

Prometheus by itself is only a time series database, the role of collecting and exposing metrics on the target system is left to purpose-built exporters. The wiki [Prometheus(2022)] list thousands of exporters, from the ubiquitous `node_exporter`, to domain-specific exporters unrelated to computing like `craftbeerpi_exporter`. The exporters are simple web servers that return a text string containing a list of metrics when their endpoint is polled by Prometheus, or `curl` when testing them. An example of the metrics format is in Figure 3, each line returned is either a comment or a single metric with possibly multiple labels. In this case, this is the number of CPU seconds spent in each mode. In the previous example, the mode and the CPU core number are available as labels, which are used to filter and make aggregation in queries, like summing all the cores in a node that are currently idle. Prometheus also supports counters and their rollover, using counters instead of gauges solves the problem with low-frequency polling that can happen when the workload varies a lot between two samples. With a performance counter, the average will be correct, while a gauge might over or under-report depending on when the sample is taken. This sampling problem is present with the data returned by NVIDIA's API because they are gauges and not counters, unlike the kernel where counters are used for the CPU cores.

For HPC and Openstack, multiple exporters had to be created to collect the information we were looking for.

1) `lustre_exporter`: The initial exporter we used in production was `lustre_exporter` [Handzik et al.(2022)] developed by HPE. Lustre [OpenSFS and EOFS(2022)] by itself can tag each RPC with a short ID on every RPC sent to the servers since version 2.3, the recommended way to use this is to use the scheduler job ID on the compute nodes. On

Fig. 3. Example of metrics returned by `node_exporter`

```

$ curl 127.0.0.1:9100/metrics
[...]
# HELP node_cpu_seconds_total Seconds the CPUs spent in each mode.
# TYPE node_cpu_seconds_total counter
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="idle"} 3.37838824e+06
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="iowait"} 3043.15
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="irq"} 0
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="nice"} 1881.87
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="softirq"} 4537.13
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="steal"} 0
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="system"} 79434.52
node_cpu_seconds_total{cpu="0",mode="user"} 307960.94

```

login nodes, the process name with the UID is used so we can identify some reoccurring abuse like doing a `touch` on all the files on scratch.

This enabled us to quickly have some monitoring of the Lustre servers and all IO done by the jobs. The main problem we encountered with this exporter was the only label included was the job ID used in the Slurm job. This is fine to get the statistics of a single job but was insufficient to find the culprit when a user had thousands of small jobs doing 100 IOPS each since we could not aggregate those statistics by users.

2) *lustre_exporter_slurm*: To fix this lack of labels, we had to develop a small middleware called *lustre_exporter_slurm* [Guilbault(2022a)] acting as a proxy between Prometheus and *lustre_exporter*. The role of this exporter is to intercept the metrics, find the job ID of each returned metric, and use that job ID to do a lookup in the MySQL database of Slurm to find the username and account of that job. Once this information is found, the new labels are added, and Prometheus gathers the metrics with those additional labels. The middleware approach was selected because it enables us to do caching and prevent the Lustre servers from having to access the MySQL database directly.

This exporter was presented at LUG2021 [Guilbault(2021)] with an initial prototype of the portal.

3) *slurm-job-exporter*: This exporter [Guilbault(2022b)] role is to gather the job statistics using the cgroups and NVIDIA's API.

On our clusters, we have a subset of nodes that can be requested on a by-core basis, so whole node statistics are not enough because we need to attribute the resources used to the correct users and jobs within that node. Same for the GPUs, most of our nodes have 4 GPUs, and they can request only 1 if this is all they need.

Since Slurm 18.08.4, cgroups are supported when multiple jobs are running on the compute nodes. When Slurm parameter `JobAcctGatherType` is configured with `jobacct_gather/cgroup`, the processes will get assigned into cgroup dedicated to this job. The cgroups will keep track at the kernel level of some metrics like the core nanoseconds used per core and the allocated memory by type.

The directory `/sys/fs/cgroup/memory/slurm` will have a subdirectory for each user and jobs currently running on this node. Inside the job directory, various memory statistic files are stored. As an example, the file located in `uid_3007286/job_10501191/memory.stat` contains

the memory statistic for the user with the UID 3007286 and the job ID 10501191. The full format of the memory cgroup file is available in the kernel documentation [Foundation(2022)].

The stats in the cgroups are enough to capture what a job is currently doing with the memory and cores, but is lacking the information from accelerators like an NVIDIA GPU. To gather that information, the use of the appropriate API is required. For NVIDIA, there are 2 APIs, the older one is NVML, and the newest and recommended one is DCGM. NVML is easier to install and does not require a daemon but this API lack some statistics like the bandwidth on the NVLink interface and does not measure the utilization of the Tensor cores, FP16, FP32, and FP64. DCGM is now the preferred API but the *slurm-job-exporter* kept its backward compatibility with NVML. MIG devices are also collected by the exporter.

4) *slurm-exporter*: Some metrics like the account priorities in Slurm are collected with the *slurm-exporter* [et al.(2017)]. This exporter is also used to gather the RPC statistics from the Slurm controller and the number of jobs running on each partition, the number of cores allocated, and a few other metrics.

5) *libvirt_exporter*: The largest black box we had for monitoring was the Openstack cluster. This cluster is available so the researcher can deploy applications that do not fit in a traditional HPC environment, like a public web portal or a Windows VM.

Before gathering the statistics, we had the usual suspicions that the cloud resources were underused simply based on the stats from *node_exporter* on each hypervisor. The existing *libvirt_exporter* [Naser et al.(2020)] had almost what we required, but the lack of an instance name, user, and project labels made it impossible to assign the used resource correctly. That information already existed inside the XML file of the VM definition within *libvirt*. We had to fork [et al.(2022)] the original project to capture the required labels. Since all the data is already local in the hypervisor node when the VM is running, this exporter does not require external access to Openstack's API or database.

This exporter collects metrics at the hypervisor level, regardless of the cooperation of the VM. Used CPU cycles, network interfaces, disk IOPS, and bandwidth are collected. The memory is a bit more complicated to measure accurately because the hypervisor is not aware of the internal memory management of the VM, but the presence of the memory balloon configured by default in modern distribution is used to approximate how much memory is not currently allocated inside the VM.

6) *Jobscrip collector*: The jobscrip collector is a small daemon running on the *slurmctld* host. It will collect the jobscrip of each job from `/var/spool/slurmctld/hash*/job*/scrip` and sent it to the portal using a REST API. The jobscrip is then stored in the MySQL database of the portal and made available in the portal for each job.

IV. THE PORTAL

Before building this portal, we had a few dashboards created in Grafana [Grafana Labs(2018)]. Those dashboards were only available to system administrators using a VPN. Since we could not filter or post-process the data before displaying it, we could not directly expose Grafana to the end users.

A. Django

The Python framework Django was selected because of previous development experiences and all the bells and whistles are included or easily available as modules. Django supports multiple database backends to store its data like cookies and custom models. MySQL was selected instead of Postgresql because Slurm and Robinhood are also using it. We decided to connect directly to the Slurm database in MySQL to prevent any timeout problems with the production `slurmd` and `slurmctld` daemons. A read-only user was created to access the production databases of Slurm and Robinhood and an ORM model was created to map useful tables to the internal python representations. Each query takes only a few milliseconds and does not impact job startup or submissions.

The authentication is done in production with an IDP using the SAML protocol, Django also supports multiple authentication backends like LDAP and FreeIPA.

The deployment of the portal and collection tools was done over time, the application is also made to support partial deployment like only using the Jobstats or Cloudstats module.

With the data from Slurm, we can now get a specific job from its job ID, or get all the jobs for a user or account. With that information, we can build an HTML page for this specific job using Plotly [Plotly(2015)] JavaScript graphing library. The browser will then launch multiple HTTP queries in parallel and receive JSONs that will be used to generate the graphs. Using JavaScript increases the possibility of interactivity like mouse-over, series selection, and zoom in the displayed graph compared to generating images on the web server. This also lowers the load on the web server.

The initial use case of this portal was to find and display the worst users hitting the shared file system. Helping the top 10 users that were doing too many IOPS has resolved most of the issues with the file system and improved the performance for everybody, especially the top 10. Having the stats was essential to correctly target the right users and their research performance was improved by order of magnitudes in some cases. Without this help, they would probably have continued with suboptimal compute jobs.

The initial prototype took only a few days to get usable graphs from the stats collected. Putting a production version available for staff took a few more weeks of part-time work. The figures shown in this paper are taken from the production portal. For formatting reasons, the entire page is not included in this document since it's too long and badly formatted for print. A printable or exportable version of the pages on the portal could be developed if researchers require it to support their publications.

Job analysis

This job is using multiple nodes
Line 27: GROMACS preprocessor should be used on a login node
Line 29: GROMACS is used without srun or mpirun/mpiexec
Line 29: GROMACS is used with -nt 2 instead of -nt 96
Line 29: Multiple nodes are used without the MPI binary
Line 31: sleep command is used

Fig. 4. Automated job analysis

B. Jobstats

The first module developed for this portal was Jobstats. As the name implies, this module is used to display the recorded compute statistics for a job submitted to Slurm. The main page available to the user shows them a few graphs of their current overall use in cores, memory, and operations on the file systems. A table of their submitted job is also available with a link to the page for each job. This table can be sorted and filtered to only show jobs with a specific status, like in progress, completed, node-failed, etc.

Since we have the submitted job script and the statistic of each job, we can do some basic job analysis based on the content and the resources used. Most low-hanging fruits are detected in this analysis such as only using 1 core when multiple are requested, and only using the first node with code that can't run in parallel over multiple nodes.

The content of the script is also parsed with various regular expressions to detect misused applications, one example is using GROMACS with the wrong number of threads passed as parameters, this is shown in figure 4. Some recommendations are also given to the user to help them fix their job and links to documentation are provided.

Figure 5 shows a table with information about the allocated resources, and what was used. Some scheduling information about when it was submitted, how long it spent in the queue, the time it started and ended, and what was the LevelFS (priority) when this job started is shown in this table. Some information about the energy used and CO2 released are also available in this table. When the cost calculation is enabled, this table also shows the internal cost based on the amortization of the hardware and energy used for power and cooling. If the cloud cost is configured, it will also display an estimate based on the cost per hour of similar hardware in commercial clouds.

Figure 6 shows a job requesting four cores but only using one, we can also see that the process was not bound to a specific core. The Y-axis is scaled based on the allocated cores

Scheduler info

Account	Submit time	Queue time	Start time	End time	Priority
redacted	12 hours ago	2:29:49	9 hours ago	46 minutes ago	0.694925

Resources

Type	Allocated	Used
Time	11.9h	9.0h
Nodes	1	
CPU cores	4	0.98
Memory	50.0 GB	23.3 GB
GPUs per node	1x NVIDIA A100-SXM4-40GB	Cycles: 65.77%, Memory: 22.09%, Power: 46.97%
Energy		3.54 kWh
Electric car range equivalent		23.41 km
CO2 emissions		1.77 g

Fig. 5. Summary of the resources allocated and used

Fig. 6. Cores allocated and used

to make it obvious that some cores are idle. Since the cores are dedicated, nobody else on the node could use them.

In figure 7, we can see that only 25 GB out of the 50 GB allocated was used. The leftover was allocated but could not be used by any other jobs.

In figure 8, we can see that this machine learning job didn't use any Tensor cores, only FP32 were used. By comparing the CPU and GPU graphs, we can also see that around 19:00 and 00:00, the code was completely CPU bound and did not use the GPU.

In figure 9 we can see that overall, the power draw from the GPU was good, but there might still be some optimization possible to reach the 400 W available on the A100 of this node.

Other graphs such as the quantity of GPU memory used,

Fig. 7. Memory used

Fig. 8. GPU utilization

GPU memory access cycles, PCIe bandwidth, NVLink bandwidth are also available in Jobstats but not included in this document.

The IOPS and bandwidth used on the Lustre file system are also available for each user, group, and job. In figure 10 and 11, the aggregated use of a specific user is shown. Those graphs are helpful when a deluge of small jobs is causing IOPS issues on the metadata servers. Having the bandwidth also helps identify if the user is opening and closing small temporary files without using their content or if a large quantity of data is used by the job.

Some other whole node statistics are also available such as the bandwidth on the Infiniband port, the quantity of IOPS, and bytes used on the local scratch SSD. These statistics are collected with `node_exporter` and can't be broken down to the individual job when the node is shared between multiple jobs.

The last section in the Jobstats is an estimation of the power

Fig. 9. GPU power

Fig. 10. IOPS of a user on Lustre by operation type

Fig. 11. The bandwidth of a user on Lustre

used by this job, based on the power measured by `redfish_exporter` [jenningsloy318 et al.(2022)] and the power of the GPUs in the nodes, and allocated to the job. An example is shown in figure 12.

For a CPU job, the node power is allocated based on the ratio of allocated cores on this node. So a 32-core job on a 64-core node will get half the power of the node allocated. Dividing the whole node power on the job running on the node will include a fair share of the power used for the fans, DIMMs, network cards, and other parts of the server. Because of this fair share, the power used by smaller jobs will be quite impacted by the average of the node so this power measurement is there only to serve as an approximation of the energy required to run this job.

The idea is similar with GPU jobs, but since each GPU got an individual power measurement, we can subtract the power of the GPUs from the node, and add it to each respective job.

This power measurement is used to add the energy and CO2 emission in the table in figure 5. In this job, 3.54 kWh of energy was used and 1.77 g of CO2 was released by the use of hydroelectricity powering this cluster. This is shown to the user to create awareness of the energy used by their jobs.

C. Accountstats

Accountstats is another module available to all users. This module presents a summary of the resources used by users within a research group. An example of this graph is shown in figure 13. In this figure around October 16, we can see that

Fig. 12. Power used by a job

Fig. 13. Priority and compute usage of a group over time, the group has 269 cores allocated

Fig. 14. An overview of all cores allocated and used in Openstack, by projects (project names redacted)

jobs were submitted and started in the span of a few hours and burst over 2000 cores on an allocation of 269 cores. The graph shows an immediate response in the group priority (LevelIFS) and it went from 1.3 to 0.8. This graph is also helpful to identify problems with low priority and why jobs are currently not starting for this group. Most of the time we could see that it was caused by a high burst of jobs submitted by a single user the week before.

Other summary graphs by users in the group are also available, such as the cores, memory, and GPUs used or wasted. The aggregated IOPS and bandwidth on the file system are also available.

This enables the PI and users in the group to track who used the cluster recently and how much resources each user used within the allocation.

D. Cloudstats

With the data collected by `libvirt_exporter`, we can create an overview of resources used in all the VMs running for each project and user. On the main page accessible by staff, we show this overview containing graphs of all the cores and memory used, or not. In figure 14 we can see that we have around 1700 cores allocated to running VMs and the largest project is actively using around 400 cores. The sum of all the other projects shows an average utilization of 15 cores, out of 700 allocated. The same usage pattern also exists for memory, on the 6 TB allocated, only 1 TB is used.

Each user has access to an overview of their project, and a view of the resource used by each of their VM. Figure 15 and 16 show cores and memory use respectively. Statistics on disk IOPS, disks, and network bandwidth are also available.

E. Access control and staff-only pages

Since there are concerns about personal user data being misused, a user can only access their job data. This is enforced with a simple decorator in Django, thus the data available to

Fig. 15. Used cores in an Openstack VM

Fig. 16. Used memory in an Openstack VM

the user is more limited than what can be read from a `squeue` command on a login node.

Staff members can access all the statistics and can view a leaderboard of the largest CPU and GPU consumers and also the top users on the file systems. A redacted example of this leaderboard is in figure 17, this table has been edited to show an example of a good user and a user wasting resources, the user currently wasting resources had the 5th largest quantity of GPUs currently running. We can also observe that both users are likely single-threaded and CPU bound because there are as many cores being actively used as there are allocated GPUs. Colors are used to bring the attention of the analyst to the worst offenders.

This leaderboard can be searched and sorted as required by the analyst.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Having a centralized place to view the usage of the cluster and each job helped us to identify problems and improve the cluster usage. We can now see the impact of a job on the cluster and the users can see their impact on the cluster. Without profiling every job, we can now quickly identify the jobs and users that are wasting resources. This allows us to quickly identify the problem and take action by either killing or simply informing the user depending on the quantity of resources being wasted. Our analysts are now using this portal to be proactive and help users improve their jobs and reduce the impact on the cluster.

Future work includes adding other sources of information such as the Syslogs in ElasticSearch. We are also looking at

Username	Allocated GPUs	Used GPUs	Fully used GPUs equivalent	Allocated cores	Used cores	Allocated memory	Max memory	Wasting
good_user	92	80.0	70.9	368.0	92.69	4.94 TB	1.37 TB	OK
user_needs_help	20	18.0	0.2	80.0	20.15	343.6 GB	327.3 GB	GPUs

Fig. 17. Leaderboard for GPU jobs, the second user is currently wasting 20 GPUs. The CPU leaderboard is similar, but without the GPUs columns.

improving the automated detection of jobs that are wasting resources and the ability to automatically kill them. Having the portal reach out by itself to the user by sending them alert when their jobs are wasting resources would be a great improvement and will reduce the workload of our analysts. Since we gather all the statistics about the jobs running under each allocation, this source of information could be used to improve the allocation process and reward good usage.

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